

THE ANALYSIS OF VALENCY COMPONENT AT THE SYNTACTIC LEVEL

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Annotation: The present article deals with the theory of syntactic valency, principles of defining syntactic valency, and revealing syntaxemes expressed by valency components in English simple sentences from the structural syntax point of view.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается теория синтаксической валентности, принципы их определения и выявление синтаксем выраженные валентными компонентами в английских простых предложениях с точки зрения структурного синтаксиса.

Аннотация: Мазкур мақола синтактик валентлик назарияси, синтактик валентликни аниқлаш тамойиллари ва инглиз тилидаги содда гапларни компонентларга ҳамда синтаксемаларга ажратиб таҳлил қилиш асосида валентли компонентлар ифодалаган синтаксемаларни структурал синтаксис нуқтаи назаридан очиб беришга қаратилган.

Key words: *valency, analysis of component, junctional model, syntaxeme analysis, transformational technique, nuclear predicative, non-nuclear predicative, subordinate relations.*

A great number of researches have been done to solve issues such as studying controversial problems of the traditional syntax, distinguishing semantic, lexical and stylistic approaches from one another in order to clarify the meaning of the theory of valency, as well as, principles of identifying monovalent and polyvalent syntactic units in the simple structure of the English speech. In addition to this, in most studies on various issues of valency theory the problem is researched through lexical-semantic features of the verb. Scientific research is being conducted so as to determine phonological, lexical and semantic spheres along with semantics of syntactic valency and syntactic units. There are various approaches to the theory of valency at the syntactic level, which is very essential in linguistics. The need to entirely cover this issue from the point of view of the syntactic and semantic level of the language determines the necessity to carry out research on this area based on the new approaches and the relevance of the topic.

Also in Uzbek linguistics, the research on the theory of valency within the framework of language levels is carried out mainly in accordance to the lexical characteristics of the verb. Even though having done great achievements in studying the role

and significance of lexical and semantic valency of language units, there is a shortage of monographic works on valency in the syntactic level. Furthermore, there is a need to use new methods of syntactic analysis, since the traditional method of analyzing the sentence by dividing it into parts does not fully justify itself. In this research article, one of the pressing problems is to reveal the essence of the view that any independent word group can have valency at the syntactic level through modern methods of studying sentence structure, namely, separation into components and syntaxemes (modeling), and the use of various methods of transformation. Despite having done a plethora of works on syntactic level in linguistics, existing studies differ from one another in accordance to the approaches to the issue.

In order to practically analyze the topic on the basis of linguistic methods undergraduate students can use subjects such as “Theoretical and practical grammar” and graduate students will use subjects such as “The significant problems of theoretical grammar”, “Linguistic methods”, “Theory of translation”, “Comparative typology”, “Syntactical-semantics” during special course and seminars as well as while creating educational, methodological manuals, textbooks on these fields. BO'LADIMI?

In linguistics the concept of valency was first used by the Russian linguist scientist, S.D.Katsnelson giving the followings definition: “The way a word joins other words in a certain combination during its participation in speech is called valency” [1, 132]. Since then, Russian linguists have been trying to determine valency, following S.D.Katsnelson, and European linguists following L.Tesniere [1, 156]. L.Tesniere divided verbs into four main groups to determine the valency based on the concept of “verbocentrism” [2, 156].

I.Erben, on the other hand, divides simple statement into four models arguing that not only subject and object, but adverbial modifier, predicative attribute and predicatives also help determine verb valency in the sentence structure [3, 89].

According to X.L.Somers, “... approaching valency only within the context of verb is limited by the number of objects it join, which does not fully verifies the theory of valency” [4, 113]. In addition, Professor A.M.Mukhin emphasizes: “Always considering the verb as the structural center of speech leads to some ambiguities” [5, 69].

Relying on verb in the statement structure or syntactical units in the function of predicate in the functional-syntactical level of the valency, if the division of components into mono or bivalent, polyvalent, obligatory or optional valent, strong or weak valent is not thoroughly elucidated based on the specific linguistic methods, any researchers will be unable to comprehensively express the valency at the syntactic level.

In this article, we aim to clarify the theory of valency on the basis of syntactic relations, relying on the 5 syntactic relations (nuclear predicative, subordinative, coordinative, non-nuclear predicative and appositive) out of 7 syntactic relations, which are created by A.M.Mukhin [6, 69]. Syntactic valency is determined based on the number of syntactic relations, that is, it is proven through junctional models that each syntactic unit in a sentence can possess valency. If they are connected by one syntactic relation, it is called

univalent or monovalent; if they participate by two or three syntactic relations, they are called bivalent or trivalent or polyvalent components.

Based on examples collected from fiction, it was found that univalent components can replace nuclear components ($NP_1 \cdot NP_2$ – subject and predicate) and non-nuclear dependent component ($\tilde{N}D$ – secondary part of sentence) in the sentence structures.

According to the following example, we shall analyze univalent syntactic units in all three syntactic positions based on the junctional and componential models

Walter's death had been a shock to her (SM, 202).

In this sentence structure above each syntactic unit is considered a univalent component, because each one of them gets into syntactic relation. Nuclear components – *death* that replaces nuclear predicative 1 (NP_1 - subject), *had been a shock* that replaces nuclear predicative 2 (NP_2) are syntactic units that are connected on the basis of nuclear predicative relations. Syntactic units such as *Walter's* and *to her* that replace the component like non-nuclear dependent ($\tilde{N}D$) are considered univalent components, are also connected with syntactic units such as nuclear predicative 1 (NP_1) - *death* and nuclear predicative 2 (NP_2) - *had been a shock* on the basis of subordinate relation. Nuclear predicative 1 (NP_1) and nuclear predicative 2 (NP_2) that are replaced by syntactic units are considered main or supporting components in relation to dependent components. The componential model of analyzed sentence structure is expressed as following: *Walter's*– (Sps), the syntactic unit that replaces $\tilde{N}D$ expresses noun in the possessive case, *death* – (S) in place of NP_1 expresses noun in the nominative case, *had been a shock*– (cS) in place of NP_2 expresses linking verb and noun, *to her* – (prPnob) in place of $\tilde{N}D$ expresses preposition and objective case in the personal pronoun.

Non-nuclear dependent components, the example of which is given below, can be identified with the help of transformation:

Walter's death had been a shock to her → ...*death had been a shock* ...

Even though we omit non-nuclear dependent components, the main meaning of the statement stays unchanged. However, it is impossible to omit nuclear components:

Walter's death had been a shock to her ≠ *Walter's ... had been a shock to her* ≠ *Walter's death ... to her*.

As the result of transformation is obvious, if nuclear components omitted, the meaning of the statement can be incomprehensible. In addition to this, we have analyzed the connection of components in relation to main part and a second dependent part on the basis of subordinate relation.

In English in simple sentence structure syntactic units are considered trivalent components if they participate in based on the three syntactic relations. Analyzing collected materials on the topic, we have witnessed that trivalent components, as said in a traditional term, can perform the task of attribute and connect with other components on the basis of

three syntactic relations. In the point view of V.O.Pavlov, if one of them is connected explicitly (directly) on the basis of appositive syntactic relation, the other two types of syntactic relations are manifested implicitly (indirectly) [7, 19]. Implicitly connected syntactic relations and their differential syntactic signs can be proved in various ways of transformation methods.

Trivalent components can occur in the following syntactic relations:

1. In sentence structure, while analyzing *trivalent elements that come in place of non-nuclear dependent appositive predicative 1* ($\tilde{N}AP_1$), if they are connected to nuclear predicative 1 component (NP_1 – subject) of the sentence directly on the basis of appositive relation, it was found that they get into nuclear predicative relation with the components of nuclear predicative 2 (NP_2 – predicate) and nuclear predicative 1 indirectly. So, the component of non-nuclear appositive predicative 1 considered a trivalent if it possesses the feature of connecting on the basis of one appositive and two nuclear predicative relations. This can be illustrated with the following example below:

In the sentence of *Wouldn't you agree, Miss Ladram? Miss Ladram* replaces the component of non-nuclear appositive predicative 1 ($\tilde{N}AP_1$). The junction and componential models of this sentence can be explained as in the following:

In the sentence above we will explain that the syntactic unit, *Miss Ladram* is a trivalent component based on the transformation method as follows:

(2) *Wouldn't you agree, Miss Ladram?* → (2a) *you are Miss Ladram.*

So, if in this sentence *Miss Ladram*, which replaces $\tilde{N}AP_1$ component, and *you*, which replaces the component of nuclear predicative 1, explicitly interact with syntactic unit based on the appositive relation, nuclear predicative implicitly interacts. In addition to this, in order to implicitly identify the third nuclear predicative relation using the method of changing places of transformation, it creates an opportunity to change the component *you* in place of nuclear predicative 1 (NP_1) and *Miss Ladram* in place of the component of non-nuclear appositive predicative 1 ($\tilde{N}AP_1$):

(2) *Wouldn't you agree, Miss Ladram?* → (26) *Wouldn't Miss Ladram agree?*

As a result of transformation it is illustrated as in the following:

(26) *Wouldn't Miss Ladram agree?*

In world linguistics the theory of valency is studied based on the concept of verbocentrism, lexicographically connecting with the lexical meaning of the verb, in most cases, giving a hint to semantic valency, verbs are divided into valencies based on the lexical level of the language. However, such views unable to syntactically direct researchers to a smooth way. In our opinion, valency in the sentence structure is not only a phenomenon

specific to verb, but if any syntactic unit that take part in the sentence based on one syntactic relation – it is considered a univalent component, if two syntactic relations – bivalent, if three syntactic relations – trivalent component [8, 24; 9,24].

Relying on the nuclear predicative, subordinate, coordinative, non-nuclear predicative and appositive syntactic relations, on the data of syntactic relations the theory of valency was clarified.

The external structure of the sentences that univalent and multivalent components took part in was demonstratively analyzed with the help of componential and junctional models. If the syntaxemes identified through the methods of junction, component and syntaxeme analysis continue to be studied as a separate language material, they may become the basis to create linguistic support for automatic translation in computer linguistics.

Bibliography

1. Кацнельсон С.Д. О грамматической категории. Вестник ЛГУ, 1948.– №2. – С.130-138.
2. Теньер Л. Основы структурного синтаксиса. Перевод с фран. – Москва: Наука, 2007.–670с.
3. Erben J. Abriss der Deutschen Grammatik. 9. Unverändert. Auf 1. –Berlin, 1966.–316s.
4. Somers H.L. On the Validaty of the Complement – adjunct distinction in Valency Grammar // Linguistics, 1984.– V.22. №4.– P. 113-126.
5. Мухин А.М. Модели внутринных синтаксических связей предложений // Вопросы языкознания.– Москва: 1970.– №4.– С.68-80.
6. Мухин А.М. Структура предложений и их модели. – Ленинград, Ленинград отд.: Наука, 1968.–230с.
7. Павлов В.О. Об имплекативности валентности прилагательных // Герценовские чтения. Иностранные языки. Материалы конференции. С. – Петербург: Образование, 1994.–С.18-24.
8. Asadov R.M. Valency of syntactic units with nuclear and non-nuclear predicative relations // Буюк Ипак Йўлида умуминсоний ва миллий қадриятлар: тил, таълим ва маданият (Халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари). – Samarqand, 2020. – P. 106-109.
9. R.M.Asadov, Sh.H.Mardiyeva Syntactic valency of predicative components nomli ilmiy maqola 2024-yil 8-9-noyabr (159-162-betlar) doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/3spyyx11>